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Mordenisation of Awadh Army after the Battle of Buxar

Brijesh Kumar Shukla*

A general notion in the study of India's colonial past is that after the treaty of Buxar, Awadh seized to be a powerful state. Militarily it was ruined by the English and Nawab Shuja-ud-daulah never tried to get rid of English yoke and completely surrendered. The present aims at bursting this myth. It argues that Awadh tried to revamp its military with help of French officers.

Nawab Shuja-ud-daulah ascended to throne in late 1754 after obtaining the imperial appointment from puppet Emperor Alamgir II. Though there was an incident, to which Richard B. Barnett explains as having flavor of scandal, due to heedless and gratuitously offensive action of the young Nawab.¹

During Shuja's early years, he also has to face the many foes as it was common in 18th century north India. The politics in North India was such that there was no permanent enemy or eternal friend. Richard B Barnett has aptly worded the situation as '*The regional powers of upper India, often combined with outside forces such as the Afghans, were continually engaged in testing one another's strength, and alliances were made, exploited, and broken with only temporary profit or advantage in view.*'² In these uncertain political surroundings the only force one could trust was its own might.

I

It is known that Shuja-ud-daula's early political and military actions point out that maintaining a strong and disciplined military was of paramount importance for the Awadh regime, not for aggression but also for survival in fragile eighteenth century's upper India.

In October 1764, at the battlefield of Buxar, Company's army under the command of Maj Hector Munro gained a narrow victory over the combined imperial army led by Shuja-ud-daulah. The fight was so intense that even many company officers including Shuja's French commanders repeatedly concluded that the British had lost.³ It was the superior discipline of battered company units that tilted the result in Company's favour.

In spite of being numerically superior and equal in military strategy and tactics Shuja lost the battle to company. His defeat can be attributed to two factors, one, 'astounding mercenary orientation of Shuja's Mughal and Durrani troopers who left their assigned positions after initial skirmish to plunder first the Company's, then the nawab's, baggage trains. Second, commander of Shuja's left wing left the command and fled the field at a crucial point and in order to cover him his units came across Gentil's and Madec's highly effective artillery fire, thus neutralizing the Frenchmen's activity at a very crucial juncture.'⁴

One of his first actions after the humiliation at Baksar was to carry out a complete reorganization and reform of his army which was not mentioned by the 1765 treaty. He disbanded all his remaining Mughal contingents since they had proven highly unreliable, retaining only those officers who were related to him or to the royal family. He then began recruiting new units and officers on a large scale, mostly from among his Rajput, Brahmin, and Shaikhzada subjects but also from the armies of other regional rulers and local chiefs. Within eighteen months he had brought together more than 30,000 troops, both cavalry and infantry, training and organizing them after the European model with the assistance and advice of the French, Armenian and Abyssinian officers who had served Mir Qasim.

This policy was not new for the Nawab. He was a keen observer of the political situation of then India and had already started the process of modernising his army even before 1765.⁵ He had already inducted famous French freebooters Sombre and Madec in his army.⁶ Desertion of small but well-disciplined companies under the French officers Madec and Gentil, just before the battle of Buxar caused considerable alarm to the British side.⁷ After the battle of Buxar, he had to remove both of them from his service on account of growing English pressure.

It is understandable, then, why military preparedness remained the Nawab's foremost concern. The greater the size and the more polished the skill of his army, however, the more alarmed some of the British officers on the fringes of his territory became. Captain Gabriel Harper stationed in Faizabad as the Company's representative, made a full analysis of Shuja's forces in late 1768 as Awadh's military reorganization was being completed. This analysis portrays the composition and size of the Awadh army and nobility after most of the itinerant Persian and Durrani Afghan units were disbanded and new indigenous elements were enlisted to replace them.⁸ Nawab also hired the European instructors to train his army⁹

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In 1771 Shuja took into his service a member of the Maratha nobility, Copal Rao, who brought with him 1,500 cavalry for a salary of Rs. 49,000 per month. Together with the two Gosain brothers, he was one of but three officers who held the power of the dastkhat (this means signature, and it entitled a commander to enlist and dismiss troops without the Nawab's permission). It apparently mattered little to Shuja that his army was so heterogeneous: it was more important that he was rid of the Mughal elements who had served him so poorly at Baksar. Heterogeneity was only one feature of Shuja's army.

Another feature of Awadh's forces deserves mention is Nawab's considerable investment in artillery, which according to Harper totaled 268 cannon of various calibers.¹⁰ Harper noted on his report that both cavalry and infantry "are excellent troops," not merely the ragtag collection of mercenary hangers-on that made up the typical Indian regime's army.

II

Even before the Buxar, the Nawab had maintained a decent artillery. The artillery taken by the English in the battle field of Buxar, and in the pursuit of the enemy, amounted to 133 pieces of various sizes.¹¹ As stated earlier, in post Buxar phase, Nawab with the help of newly recruited French officers exerted all his efforts and resources to resurrect his military capabilities. Artillery, specially, was given more attention.

The French adventurers established arsenals and foundries for producing firearms of latest European technology.¹² Military laboratories were set up at various places for the production of war equipments. During the period 22 foundries and armories were established in Awadh. Delamarr a famous military scientist made immense contribution in this regard by producing high quality firearms in Awadh.

Faizabad became the hub of this new arms production activity. The Faizabad foundry was massive in built and reputed for high production capacity. It was reported that it alone provided war equipments to about ten battalions.¹³ Artificers were employed to manufacture small arms. In the Faizabad foundry 500 artificers had been employed who produced 150 to 200 firelocks of European design every month.¹⁴ The English also praised the quality production of small arms of Awadh foundry and found them as good as of Europe.¹⁵

One contemporary source writes that By 1775 there were two arsenals in Faizabad. They were built on the different sides of the city- one in south and the other outside the inner circles in the north near a sarai.¹⁶ Even after the death of Shuja the place still had huge storage of iron, copper, and lead which was used for artillery ammunition production.¹⁷

Apart from producing firearms of latest European types, the arsenals and foundries of Awadh also gained high reputation for their quality production and became a cause of alarm to English. This artillery attained such efficiency that Colonel Smith, Commander of English troops at Allahabad regarded it as a serious menace to Company in Bengal.¹⁸

We have contemporary evidences which testify that the English too acknowledged the higher quality and quantity of Awadh foundries' battlefield-ready production.¹⁹ Governor of Bengal, Verelst particularly reported the quality of thy fabrication of small arms in Awadh by calling it '*an amazing improvement and said in terms of quality it was equal to what was imported to India.*'²⁰ Awadh acquired high reputation for its firelocks. According to William Hoey's Memoirs of Faizabad, a contemporary source, by 1770-71, the effectiveness of Awadh firelocks reached its zenith when it superseded even the English firelocks.²¹

Awadh's technicians enhanced skills in casting of quality weapons was also noted by Comte de Modave when he visited Shuja-ud-daula's arsenal at Faizabad in 1773. He claimed that the guns and bayonets manufactured there were 'almost as well as in our workshops in Europe'.²²

In 1764, some French troops of company's army decided to desert to Shuja-ud-daula. Head of these deserters was Delamarr who was known for his scientific knowledge. He and his associates made valuable contribution in the production of efficient firearms. The English later claimed that the Nawab himself had approached Delamarr to join his services.²³

The Nawab also undertook the task of erecting fortified buildings. In 1772, he decided to build a new powerful fort north of Faizabad. Charles de Canaple, a French engineer, was entrusted with the task including the design of the fort and the management of the work.²⁴ Gentil, in his unpublished letter has noted that 30,000 workers were hired who worked night and day under Canaple's direction to build the ramparts and bastions of the massive fort. Modave wrote '*the fort, built by a Frenchman..., is a regular hexagon: completed to its perfection it would undoubtedly be the strongest fortress in Hindustan*'²⁵

III

Shuja, confident of his rejuvenated military potential, tried to tilt the balance of power between him and the English to his favour. In early 1767 he requested Company to completely evacuate and handover the fort of Chunar.²⁶ Though the request of Nawab was denied yet the Calcutta Council believed that confident nawab may 'come to an open rupture' and requested court of directors for reinforcing the garrison.²⁷

On 24th October 1768, Colonel Smith commander of Allahabad reported to Bengal Select Committee about Awadh Army. He wrote:

“it is with concern, I learn the state of ShujahDowlah’s army. ... he has five battalions of sepoy complete,...; two other battalions are now raising. He can already bring more pieces of artillery into the field than we have with the second and third brigades.”²⁸

This observation of an opponent seems very important while analyzing the revamping efforts of Shuja’s army. Increased importance of infantry unit along with good numbers of artillery gun clearly resembles the new era of French commanders in Awadh army. In spite of restrictions on entry of Europeans into Awadh, the strength of exclusive French contingent increased to 600 from 400.²⁹

By 1770-71, Infantry and artillery acquired supreme importance in the military setup and the cavalry force which had numbered about 30,000 during the battle of Buxar was reduced to a little more than 5000.³⁰ Persian correspondence of aforesaid period is also testimony of the fact that the efforts put in by the Nawab and French commanders greatly enhanced the military potential of Awadh.³¹ Court of directors of Company had also expressed concerns over efficient increase of battalions of Awadh army while observing on Secret Consultations sent to them on 18th April 1775, after the death of Shuja. They wrote:

*‘that the late Vizier entertained a considerable number of Europeans in his service, by which means he had formed a sepoy establishment of nearly 20 battalions by no means inferior in appearance or discipline to the most perfect of our battalions...’*³²

IV

It goes exclusively to the credit of Shuja-ud-daula that during his lifetime he had maintained relations with the Company so tactfully and diplomatically that the British could not succeed in any vigorous interference in matters of Awadh. Though the treaty of Allahabad brought a rope around his neck but throughout his life he not only evaded that but also made consistent efforts for a getaway. Nawab deftly ignored company’s demand, their injunctions and incendiary reports and retained his French corps until his death in January 1775. In 1775, there was news in Company circle that through his French commanders he had started negotiations with the France to attack the English dominion in India.³³

Unfortunately, the sudden death of the Nawab in 1775 arrested the entire process of military reforms which had gained considerable momentum under the French officers’ supervision. In the death of the Nawab, the English found a golden opportunity to have the French expelled from Awadh.³⁴ Court of directors viewed Awadh’s infantry battalions as serious threat. They ordered the Calcutta Council to get the battalions dismissed and all French to be expelled.³⁵ English company was ordered by the Court of Directors to include this as a clause in the treaty with new nawab as a mandatory condition of English support.³⁶

New nawab Asaf-ud-daula was pressurized and forced to dissolve his French force.³⁷ Nawab’s arsenal was put under the command of Captain Claude Martin.³⁸ Gentil had to leave Awadh. He was offered lucrative salary by the Emperor Shah Alam and also by the Nepalese king.³⁹ But he preferred to return to France.⁴⁰ He wrote his memoirs and dedicated it to his employer and true friend Shuja-ud-daula.⁴¹

This sudden downfall in the military potential of Awadh is the testimony of the fact that it was the French who were the backbone of the military reforms of Awadh. Once they were ousted, the whole military mechanism of Awadh collapsed. Nawabs became increasingly dependent on company and could never even imagine resisting the highhandedness of Company.

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